

ON THE THIRD SMARANDACHE CONJECTURE ABOUT PRIMES

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Abstract . In this paper we basically verify the third Smarandache conjecture on prime.

Key words . Smarandache third conjecture, prime , gap.

For any positive integer n , let $P(n)$ be the n -th prime. Let k be a positive integer with $k > 1$, and let

$$(1) \quad c(n,k) = (P(n+1))^{1/k} - (P(n))^{1/k} .$$

Smarandache [3] has been conjectured that

$$(2) \quad C(n,k) < \frac{2}{k} .$$

In [2], Russo verified this conjecture for $P(n) < 2^{25}$ and $2 \leq k \leq 10$. In this paper we prove a general result as follows .

Theorem . If $k > 2$ and $n > C$, where C is an effectively computable absolute constant, then the inequality (2) holds.

Proof . Since $k > 2$, we get from (1) that

$$(3) \quad C(n,k) = \frac{P(n+1) - P(n)}{(P(n+1))^{(k-1)/k} + (P(n+1))^{(k-2)/k} (P(n))^{1/k} + \dots + (P(n))^{(k-1)/k}}$$

$$< \frac{P(n+1) - P(n)}{k(P(n))^{(k-1)/k}} \leq \frac{2}{k} \left[\frac{(P(n+1) - P(n))}{2(P(n))^{2/3}} \right] .$$

By the result of [1], we have

$$(4) \quad P(n+1) - P(n) < C(a)(P(n))^{11/20+a} ,$$

for any positive number a , where $C(a)$ is an effectively

computable constant depending on a . Put $a=1/20$. Since $k \geq 3$ and $(k-1)/k \geq 2/3$, we see from (3) and (4) that

$$(5) \quad C(n,k) < \frac{2}{k} \left(\frac{C(1/20)}{2(P(n))^{1/15}} \right).$$

Since $C(1/20)$ is an effectively computable absolute constant, if $n > C$, then $2(P(n))^{1/15} > C(1/20)$. Thus, by (5), the inequality (2) holds. The theorem is proved.

References

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